

Totally Umbilical Hemislant Submanifolds of Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian Manifold

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Abstract: This paper is summarized as follows. In the first section we have given a brief history about slant and hemi-slant submanifold of Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold. This section is followed by some preliminaries about Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold. Finally, we have derived some interesting results on the existence of extrinsic sphere for totally umbilical hemi-slant submanifold of Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold.

Key Words: Totally Umbilical, hemi-slant submanifold, extrinsic sphere.

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§1. Introduction

Chen in 1990 [2] initiated the study of slant submanifold of an almost Hermitian manifold as a natural generalization of both holomorphic and totally real submanifolds. After this many research papers on slant submanifolds appeared. The notion of slant immersion of a Riemannian manifold into an almost contact metric manifold was introduced by A. Lotta in 1996 [5]. He studied the intrinsic geometry of 3-dimensional non-anti-invariant slant submanifolds of K-contact manifold. Further investigation regarding slant submanifolds of a Sasakian manifold [8] was done by Cabrerizo et al. in 2000. Khan et al. in 2010 defined and studied slant submanifolds in Lorentzian almost paracontact manifolds [14].

The idea of hemislant submanifold was introduced by Carriazo as a particular class of bislant submanifolds, and he called them antislant submanifolds in [9]. Recently, in 2009 totally umbilical slant submanifolds of Kaehler manifold was studied by B.Sahin. Later on, in 2011 Siraj Uddin et.al. studied totally umbilical proper slant and hemislant submanifolds of an LP-cosymplectic manifold [21].

Our present note deals with a special kind of manifold i.e. Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold. At first we give some introduction about the development of such manifold. An almost contact metric structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) on \tilde{M} is called a trans-Sasakian structure [17] if (MXR, J, G) belongs to the class W_4 [11], where J is the almost complex structure on (MXR) defined by

$$(J, X \frac{d}{dt}) = (\phi X - f, \eta(X) \frac{d}{dt})$$

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for all vector fields X on M and smooth functions f on $M \times R$, G is the product metric on MXR . This may be expressed by the condition

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = \alpha[g(X, Y)\xi + \eta(Y)X] + \beta[g(\phi X, Y) - \eta(Y)\phi X],$$

for some smooth functions α and β on M in [1], and we say that the trans-Sasakian structure is of type (α, β) . A trans-Sasakian structure of type (α, β) is α -Sasakian, if $\beta = 0$ and α a nonzero constant [13]. If $\alpha = 1$, then α -Sasakian manifold is a Sasakian manifold. Also in 2008 and 2009 many scientists have extended the study to Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold in [22], [18]. In this paper we have studied some special properties of totally umbilical hemislant submanifolds of Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold.

§2. Preliminaries

An n -dimensional Lorentzian manifold M is a smooth connected paracontact Hausdorff manifold with a Lorentzian metric g , that is, M admits a smooth symmetric tensor field g of type $(0, 2)$ such that for each point $p \in M$, the tensor $g_p : T_p M \times T_p M \mapsto \mathbf{R}$ is a non-degenerate inner product of signature $(-, +, +, \dots, +)$, where $T_p M$ denotes the tangent vector space of M at p and \mathbf{R} is the real number space. A non-zero vector $v \in T_p M$ is said to be timelike if it satisfies $g_p(v, v) < 0$ [16]. Let \tilde{M} be an n -dimensional differentiable manifold. An almost paracontact structure $(\phi, \xi, \eta, \tilde{g})$, where ϕ is a tensor of type $(1, 1)$, ξ is a vector field, η is a 1-form and g is Lorentzian metric, satisfying following properties :

$$\phi^2 X = X + \eta(X)\xi, \quad \eta \circ \phi = 0, \quad \phi \xi = 0, \quad \eta(\xi) = -1, \quad (2.1)$$

$$g(\phi X, \phi Y) = g(X, Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y), \quad g(X, \xi) = \eta(X). \quad (2.2)$$

for all vector fields X, Y on \tilde{M} . On \tilde{M} if the following additional condition hold for any $X, Y \in T\tilde{M}$,

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = \alpha[g(X, Y)\xi + \eta(Y)X], \quad (2.3)$$

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X \xi = \alpha \phi X, \quad (2.4)$$

where $\tilde{\nabla}$ is the Levi-Civita connection on \tilde{M} , then \tilde{M} is said to be an Lorentzian α -Sasakian manifold (Matsumoto, 1989 [15], [22]).

Let M be a submanifold of \tilde{M} with Lorentzian almost paracontact structure (ϕ, ξ, η, g) with induced metric g and let ∇ is the induced connection on the tangent bundle TM and ∇^\perp is the induced connection on the normal bundle $T^\perp M$ of M .

The Gauss and Weingarten formulae are characterized by

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X Y = \nabla_X Y + h(X, Y), \quad (2.5)$$

$$\tilde{\nabla}_X N = -A_N X + \nabla_X^\perp N, \quad (2.6)$$

for any $X, Y \in TM$, $N \in T^\perp M$, h is the second fundamental form and A_N is the Weingarten

map associated with N via

$$g(A_N X, Y) = g(h(X, Y), N). \quad (2.7)$$

For any $X \in \Gamma(TM)$ we can write,

$$\phi X = TX + FX, \quad (2.8)$$

where TX is the tangential component and FX is the normal component of ϕX . Similarly for any $N \in \Gamma(T^\perp M)$ we can put

$$\phi V = tV + fV, \quad (2.9)$$

where tV denote the tangential component and fV denote the normal component of ϕV . The covariant derivatives of the tensor fields T and F are defined as

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X \phi)Y = \tilde{\nabla}_X \phi Y - \phi \tilde{\nabla}_X Y \quad \forall X, Y \in T\tilde{M}, \quad (2.10)$$

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X T)Y = \nabla_X TY - T\nabla_X Y \quad \forall X, Y \in TM, \quad (2.11)$$

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X F)Y = \nabla_X^\perp FY - F\nabla_X Y, \quad \forall X, Y \in TM. \quad (2.12)$$

From equation (2.3), (2.5), (2.8), (2.9), (2.11) and (2.12) we can calculate

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X T)Y = \alpha[g(X, Y)\xi + \eta(Y)X] + A_{FY}X + th(X, Y), \quad (2.13)$$

$$(\tilde{\nabla}_X F)Y = -h(X, TY) + fh(X, Y). \quad (2.14)$$

A submanifold M is said to be invariant if F is identically zero, i.e., $\phi X \in \Gamma(TM)$ for any $X \in \Gamma(TM)$. On the other hand, M is said to be anti-invariant if T is identically zero, i.e., $\phi X \in \Gamma(T^\perp M)$ for any $X \in \Gamma(TM)$.

A submanifold M of \tilde{M} is called totally umbilical if

$$h(X, Y) = g(X, Y)H, \quad (2.15)$$

for any $X, Y \in \Gamma(TM)$. The mean curvature vector H is denoted by $H = \sum_{i=1}^k h(e_i, e_i)$, where k is the dimension of M and $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_k\}$ is the local orthonormal frame on M . A submanifold M is said to be totally geodesic if $h(X, Y) = 0$ for each $X, Y \in \Gamma(TM)$ and is minimal if $H = 0$ on M .

§3. Slant Submanifolds of a Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian Manifold

Here, we consider M as a proper slant submanifold of a Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold \tilde{M} . We always consider such submanifold tangent to the structure vector field ξ .

Definition 3.1 *A submanifold M of \tilde{M} is said to be slant submanifold if for any $x \in M$ and $X \in T_x M \setminus \xi$, the angle between ϕX and $T_x M$ is constant. The constant angle $\theta \in [0, \pi/2]$ is then called slant angle of M in \tilde{M} . If $\theta = 0$ the submanifold is invariant submanifold, if $\theta = \pi/2$*

then it is anti-invariant submanifold and if $\theta \neq 0, \pi/2$ then it is proper slant submanifold.

From [20] we have

Theorem 3.1 *Let M be a submanifold of an Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold \tilde{M} such that $\xi \in TM$. Then M is slant submanifold if and only if there exists a constant $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ such that*

$$T^2 = \lambda(I + \eta \otimes \xi). \quad (3.1)$$

Again, if θ is slant angle of M , then $\lambda = \cos^2 \theta$.

From [20], for any X, Y tangent to M , we can easily draw the following results for an Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold \tilde{M} ,

$$g(TX, TY) = \cos^2 \theta \{g(X, Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y)\}, \quad g(FX, FY) = \sin^2 \theta \{g(X, Y) + \eta(X)\eta(Y)\}.$$

Definition 3.2 *A submanifold M of \tilde{M} is said to be hemi-slant submanifold of a Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold \tilde{M} if there exists two orthogonal distribution D_1 and D_2 on M such that*

- (a) $TM = D_1 \oplus D_2 \oplus \langle \xi \rangle$;
- (b) The distribution D_1 is anti-invariant i.e., $\phi D_1 \subseteq T^\perp M$;
- (c) The distribution D_2 is slant with slant angle $\theta \neq \pi/2$.

If μ is invariant subspace under ϕ of the normal bundle $T^\perp M$, then in the case of hemi-slant submanifold, the normal bundle $T^\perp M$ decomposes as

$$T^\perp M = \langle \mu \rangle \oplus \phi D^\perp \oplus FD_\theta.$$

The curvature tensor of an Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold is defined as [4]

$$\tilde{R}(X, Y)Z = \tilde{\nabla}_X \tilde{\nabla}_Y Z - \tilde{\nabla}_Y \tilde{\nabla}_X Z - \tilde{\nabla}_{[X, Y]} Z. \quad (3.2)$$

For the curvature tensor we can compute by using the equations (2.10) and (3.2) the relation

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}(X, Y)\phi Z &= \phi \tilde{R}(X, Y)Z + \alpha^2 g(Y, Z)\phi X - \alpha^2 g(X, Z)\phi Y \\ &\quad - \alpha^2 g([X, Y], Z)\phi X + \alpha g(X, \tilde{\nabla}_Y Z)\xi + \alpha \eta(\tilde{\nabla}_Y Z)X \\ &\quad - \alpha g(Y, \tilde{\nabla}_X Z)\xi - \alpha \eta(\tilde{\nabla}_X Z)Y - \alpha \eta(Z)\tilde{\nabla}_X Y \\ &\quad + \alpha \eta(Z)\tilde{\nabla}_Y X - \alpha \eta(Z)[X, Y] + \alpha g(\tilde{\nabla}_X Y, Z)\xi + \alpha g(\tilde{\nabla}_Y X, Z)\xi. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Definition 3.3 *A submanifold of an arbitrary Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold which is totally umbilical and has a nonzero parallel mean curvature vector [10] is called an Extrinsic sphere.*

§4. Main Results

This section mainly deals with a special class of hemi-slant submanifolds which are totally

umbilical. Throughout this section we have considered M as a totally umbilical hemi-slant submanifold of Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold. We derive the following.

Theorem 4.1 *Let M be a totally umbilical hemi-slant submanifold of a Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold \tilde{M} such that the mean curvature vector $H \in \langle \mu \rangle$. Then one of the following is true:*

- (i) M is totally geodesic;
- (ii) M is semi-invariant submanifold.

Proof For $V \in \phi D^\perp$ and $X \in D_\theta$, we have from (2.3), (2.5), (2.6) and (2.10)

$$\alpha[g(X, V)\xi + \eta(V)X] = \nabla_X \phi V + g(X, \phi V)H + \phi A_V X - \phi \nabla_X^\perp V. \quad (4.1)$$

Since the distributions are orthogonal and from the assumption that $H \in \mu$, above equation can be written as

$$g(\nabla_X^\perp V, H) = g(V, \nabla_X^\perp H) = 0. \quad (4.2)$$

This implies $\nabla_X^\perp H \in \mu \oplus FD_\theta$. Now for any $X \in D_\theta$, we obtain on using the Gauss and Weingarten equations

$$\alpha[g(X, H)\xi + \eta(H)X] = \nabla_X^\perp \phi H - A_{\phi H} X + \phi A_H X - \phi \nabla_X^\perp H. \quad (4.3)$$

Now, using the assumption that M is totally umbilical we have

$$\alpha\eta(H)X = \nabla_X^\perp \phi H - Xg(H, \phi H) + \phi Xg(H, H) - \phi \nabla_X^\perp H. \quad (4.4)$$

On using equation (2.8) we calculate

$$\alpha\eta(H)X = \nabla_X^\perp \phi H + TXg(H, H) + FXg(H, H) - \phi \nabla_X^\perp H. \quad (4.5)$$

Taking inner product with $FX \in FD_\theta$,

$$\alpha\eta(H)g(X, FX) = g(\nabla_X^\perp \phi H, FX) + g(FX, FX)g(H, H) - g(\phi \nabla_X^\perp H, FX). \quad (4.6)$$

From Theorem 3.1 the equation becomes

$$\alpha\eta(H)g(X, FX) - g(\nabla_X^\perp \phi H, FX) - \sin^2 \theta \|H\|^2 \|X\|^2 + g(\phi \nabla_X^\perp H, FX) = 0. \quad (4.7)$$

If either $H \neq 0$ then $D_\theta = \{0\}$, i.e. M is totally real submanifold, and if $D_\theta \neq \{0\}$, M is totally geodesic submanifold or M is semi-invariant submanifold. For any $Z \in D^\perp$ from (2.13) we get

$$\nabla_Z TZ - T\nabla_Z Z = \alpha[g(Z, Z)\xi + \eta(Z)Z] + A_{FZ} Z + th(Z, Z). \quad (4.8)$$

Taking inner product with $W \in D^\perp$ the above equation takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} g(\nabla_Z TZ, W) - g(T\nabla_Z Z, W) &= \alpha[g(Z, Z)g(\xi, W) + \eta(Z)g(Z, W)] \\ &+ g(A_{FZ}Z, W) + g(th(Z, Z), W). \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

As M is totally umbilical hemi-slant submanifold and using (2.7) we can write

$$g(\nabla_Z TZ, W) - g(T\nabla_Z Z, Z) = \alpha g(Z, W)g(H, FZ) + g(tH, W)\|Z\|^2. \quad (4.10)$$

The above equation has a solution if either $H \in \mu$ or $\dim D^\perp = 1$. \square

If however, H does not belong to μ then we give the next theorem.

Theorem 4.2 *Let M be a totally umbilical hemi-slant submanifold of a Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold \bar{M} such that the dimension of slant distribution $D_\theta \geq 4$ and F is parallel to the submanifold, then M is either extrinsic sphere or anti-invariant submanifold.*

Proof Since the dimension of slant distribution $D_\theta \geq 4$, therefore we can select a set of orthogonal vectors $X, Y \in D_\theta$, such that $g(X, Y) = 0$. Now by replacing Z by TY in (3.4) we have for any $X, Y, Z \in D_\theta$,

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}(X, Y)\phi TY &= \phi\tilde{R}(X, Y)TY + \alpha^2 g(Y, TY)\phi X \\ &- \alpha^2 g(X, TY)\phi Y - \alpha^2 g([X, Y], TY) \\ &+ \alpha g(X, \tilde{\nabla}_Y TY)\xi + \alpha\eta(\tilde{\nabla}_Y TY)X \\ &- \alpha g(Y, \tilde{\nabla}_X TY)\xi - \alpha\eta(\tilde{\nabla}_X TY)Y. \end{aligned} \quad (4.11)$$

Now using equation (2.3) and (3.1) we obtain on calculation

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{R}(X, Y)FTY + \cos^2\theta\tilde{R}(X, Y)Y &= \phi\tilde{R}(X, Y)TY + \alpha^2 g(Y, TY)\phi X \\ &- \alpha^2 g(X, TY)\phi Y - \alpha^2 g([X, Y], TY) \\ &+ \alpha g(X, \tilde{\nabla}_Y TY)\xi + \alpha\eta(\tilde{\nabla}_Y TY)X \\ &- \alpha g(Y, \tilde{\nabla}_X TY)\xi - \alpha\eta(\tilde{\nabla}_X TY)Y. \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

Again if F is parallel, then above equation can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} F\tilde{R}(X, Y)TY + \cos^2\theta\tilde{R}(X, Y)Y &= \phi\tilde{R}(X, Y)TY + \alpha^2 g(Y, TY)\phi X \\ &- \alpha^2 g(X, TY)\phi Y - \alpha^2 g([X, Y], TY) \\ &+ \alpha g(X, \tilde{\nabla}_Y TY)\xi + \alpha\eta(\tilde{\nabla}_Y TY)X \\ &- \alpha g(Y, \tilde{\nabla}_X TY)\xi - \alpha\eta(\tilde{\nabla}_X TY)Y. \end{aligned} \quad (4.13)$$

Taking inner product with $N \in T^\perp M$, we obtain on using (3.3) and the orthogonality of X and Y vectors,

$$\cos^2\theta\|Y\|^2 g(\nabla_X^\perp H, N) = 0$$

The above equation has a solution if either $\theta = \pi/2$ i.e. M is anti-invariant or $\nabla_X^\perp H = 0 \forall X \in D_\theta$. Similarly for any $X \in D^\perp \oplus \langle \xi \rangle$ we can obtain $\nabla_X^\perp H = 0$, therefore $\nabla_X^\perp H = 0 \forall X \in TM$ i.e. the mean curvature vector H is parallel to submanifold, i.e., M is extrinsic sphere. Hence the theorem is proved. \square

Now we are in a position to draw our main conclusions following.

Theorem 4.3 *Let M be a totally umbilical hemi-slant submanifold of a Lorentzian (α) -Sasakian manifold \tilde{M} . then M is either totally geodesic, or semi-invariant, or $\dim D^\perp = 1$, or Extrinsic sphere, and the case (iv) holds if F is parallel and $\dim M \geq 5$.*

Proof The proof follows immediately from Theorems 4.1 and 4.2. \square

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